

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

DIDACTIC CLASSIFICATION OF TOURIST TERMS AND THEIR LEXICAL AND SEMANTIC CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract

The article provides a didactic classification of tourist terms for their systematic study and defines their lexical and semantic characteristics. The study shows that tourism terminology is closely related to the international lexicon and has a variety of semantic nuances. The classification of terms by origin, formation of synonymous series, metaphorical and metonymic extension, as well as their functionality in a professional communicative environment is justified from a linguistic point of view. As a result of the article, a scientific and theoretical basis has been formed for the application of modern didactic models in teaching tourism terminology.

Keywords: tourism terms, terminology, didactic classification, lexical features, semantic features.

Tourism, as one of the most dynamically developing areas of global economic, social and cultural life of the 21st century, is not only a separate sector of the economy, but also a complex system combining various professional fields of activity, creating a broad communication platform. The terminology developed in this field forms a professional lexical background that accurately reflects the basic concepts, processes, types of services, management mechanisms, etc. of the tourism industry. The structural and semantic features of tourism terminology are of great importance not only from a linguistic point of view, but also in its teaching and proper use in a professional communication environment.

In the modern era, the expansion of educational programs in the field of tourism, the increase in personnel training in this field and the deepening of international cooperation necessitate the systematic study of tourist vocabulary from a didactic point of view. The correct classification of terms, the characterization of their semantic shades and the definition of methods applicable in the educational process create conditions for more effective training of specialists [1].

The terminology of tourism is characterized as a multi-source lexical system: international terms, borrowings from English, regional names of tourist places and professional vocabulary related to various fields of services are the main layers that make up this system. This diversity requires the use of various didactic approaches, depending on the origin of terms, their structural and formative properties and semantic areas of development.

On the other hand, the semantic properties of tourist terms — polysemy, transposition, metaphorical extension, functional variability — require special attention when forming the professional linguistic competence of specialists working in this field. The functionality of terms both in the language system and in the educational environment makes their didactic classification an urgent scientific problem. The purpose of this article is to conduct a didactic classification of tourist terms, to determine the lexical and semantic

properties of the terms, as well as to substantiate scientific and methodological principles that can be applied in their teaching. The scientific novelty of the research lies in the analysis of tourist terms based on an integrated approach combining linguistic and didactic aspects [4].

The didactic classification of tourism terminology is a scientific and methodological approach that makes it possible to master these terms more systematically, purposefully and gradually in the educational process. The didactic classification is based not only on the formal, structural and semantic properties of terms, but also on the methods of teaching them, the contexts of practical application, functionality in professional fields and grouping according to the level of understanding of students. This approach, by systematizing the multifaceted and complex nature of tourism terminology within the didactic model, creates conditions for a balanced application of both theoretical and practical directions in the educational process.

The first main criterion of didactic classification is the principle of content orientation. This principle is based on the content load of terms, the thematic area to be mastered, and the functional content of the concepts they express, taking into account the multilevel structure of the tourism sector. From this point of view, tourist terms are grouped into several subgroups: terms related to types of tourism activities (ecotourism, rural tourism, cultural tourism, etc.); Terms related to tourism services and infrastructure (booking, registration, transfer, hospitality, tour operator, etc.); hotel and restaurant business terms (standard room, accommodation, reception, concierge, etc.); terms related to navigation and logistics (route, itinerary, destination, excursion, etc. This classification helps to maintain consistency of topics in the learning process, provides a clearer understanding of the meaningful relationships of terms and a gradual familiarization of students with the system of professional terminology [2; 5].

The second criterion is classification according to the principle of the origin of terms. Within the framework of this classification, terms are divided into three main groups: terms formed in their native language,

borrowed from different languages, and international terms. The predominance of international terminology in the field of tourism makes the study of this criterion especially important, since, knowing the etymological foundations of the terms, students more easily perceive their semantic nuances and the possibilities of functional application. The process of phonetic adaptation, morphological integration and semantic adaptation in the assimilation and teaching of international terms requires a special explanation, which is a matter requiring a separate methodological approach from a didactic point of view [7].

The third criterion is the functional and applied classification. According to this criterion, terms are grouped according to their role in real-world communication situations, interdisciplinary interactions, and the requirements of professional practice. This classification provides the study of terms in a functional context for the service sector, management, marketing and advertising, interaction with tourists, preparation of travel packages, hotel reservations and other stages of service. This approach helps students not only memorize terms, but also master their actual use, and has a significant impact on the formation of professional language competence [3].

One of the most important stages of didactic classification is the grouping of terms by degree of complexity. This grouping allows you to form a step-by-step course structure, implement step-by-step learning and apply a differentiated approach to the study of terms. Identifying simple, medium, and complex terms makes it easier for students to understand terms and build learning materials more effectively. At the same time, classification by degree of complexity makes the learning process more focused, taking into account the semantic multiplicity of terms, contextual dependence and the level of knowledge necessary for practical application. Thus, didactic classification is not only a mechanism for grouping terms, but also a comprehensive pedagogical approach that enriches the scientific and methodological foundations of training specialists in the field of tourism [6; 8].

Lexical characteristics of tourism terms:

The lexical characteristics of tourism terms are one of the main indicators of the multilevel structure of terminology. The lexical system of this field is fueled by various sources and is formed at the junction of common language vocabulary and international terminology. At the lexical level, the most striking feature is the widespread use of terms borrowed from English. As a result of the fact that the main standards of the global tourism industry are based on English, terms such as *“booking”*, *“check-in”*, *“amenities”*, *“full board”*, *“airport shuttle”*, *“tour package”* are consistently used in the tourist vocabulary of almost all languages. The integration of these borrowings into the language is accompanied by phonetic, morphological suffixation and semantic adaptation processes, which indicates the dynamic development of the lexical system.

It should also be noted that the tourist vocabulary is dominated by wordy phrases. Structures such as *“five-star hotel”*, *“standard double room”*, *“domestic tourism”*, *“cultural heritage site”*, *“airport transfer ser-*

vice” play an important role in the terminological system, as they more accurately express complex concepts. Such combinations can create certain difficulties for students from both semantic and syntactic points of view. For this reason, contextual explanation, the use of visual materials and the analysis of real examples of communication are important didactic methods in their teaching.

One of the lexical features is that a number of words and expressions used in everyday speech acquire terminological significance in the field of tourism. For example, while the word *“season”* usually means a season, in tourism it refers to specific economic and service periods such as high season, low season, and off-season. Similarly, words such as *“package”*, *“service”*, *“comfort”*, *“luxury”*, *“budget”* have specific semantic connotations in the travel industry. These processes indicate that transposition and terminological mechanisms are widely used in the lexical development of terms.

Synonyms are also often found in travel terminology. The expression of the same concept in several terms in different countries and different travel companies (*“travel agent”* – *“tour consultant”*, *“guide”* – *“tour leader”*, *“excursion”* – *“city tour”*) creates a terminological parallelism in the lexical system. In the educational process, synonymy increases the flexibility of students' understanding, allows them to realize the differences that arise when expressing the same meaning in different terms, and forms the ability to adapt in professional communication.

Another important aspect of the structural features of the tourist vocabulary is the stabilization of metaphorical and metonymic vocabulary in terminology. Expressions such as *“golden season”*, *“peak period”*, *“dead season”*, *“green tourism”*, *“blue tour”* have moved away from their original figurative meanings and have become terms denoting specific economic and environmental concepts. This demonstrates the semantic flexibility of the terminological system and the breadth of lexical creativity. All these features prove that the tourist vocabulary is a multifaceted and dynamic system in terms of meaning, structure and functionality. Therefore, from a pedagogical point of view, a separate explanation of each of the lexical features, an analysis of their semantic and functional shades, as well as their application to various textual and situational examples are of particular importance. A deep understanding of the lexical structure of travel terms teaches students not only to memorize words, but also to use them correctly, purposefully and in accordance with the context in a professional communicative environment.

Semantic features of tourist terms:

The semantic features of tourist terms reflect the multilevel semantic mechanism of the terminological system of this area, its contextual variability and the special shades of meanings that it acquires in a specialized language environment. The formation of semantics in the tourist lexicon is connected both with the terminologization of words existing in the common language and with the acquisition of new semantic functions by terms borrowed from international standards. In this regard, tourist terms are not limited to ex-

pressing only one meaning, but often carry different semantic loads in different contexts, and this feature makes their teaching more difficult, but no less interesting.

One of the main areas of semantic features is the polysemy of terms. For example, the term "package" may refer to both a set of services, a specific type of travel product, and a model for evaluating a travel package. The term "season", in contrast to the commonly used linguistic context, refers to the time stages of tourism intensity. This method of ambiguity teaches students to understand not only the lexical content of terms, but also their situational use.

Metaphorical and metonymic extensions occupy a special place in the semantic system of tourist terminology. Expressions such as "high season", "dead season", "peak period", "golden tour", "green tourism", despite their initial metaphorical origin, have already become stable semantic signs in the terminological system. Since these terms define the economic, environmental, and socio-cultural characteristics of the tourism process, the metaphorical origin acquires semantic certainty and serves as a terminological definition.

Another important aspect in the semantic field of tourist terms is the contextual dependence of meaning. Terms such as "service", "standard", "comfort", "luxury", "budget", "facility" can acquire different semantic shades depending on the environment in which they are used. For example, "comfort" may refer to the comfort of a certain type of hotel room, the level of airline tickets, and the number of additional services in travel packages. For this reason, semantic analysis requires a contextual approach in the learning process and develops students' ability to choose the meaning appropriate to the situation.

Transposition plays an important role in the formation of semantic structure in tourism terminology. Words such as "Guide", "route", "trip", "transfer", "booking", went beyond their original ordinary meaning and began to carry specialized semantic functions in the system of professional terminology. This process indicates the semantic development of the language, as well as the lively and action-oriented nature of terminology.

Another direction in the development of semantic features is *antonomasia* and the transformation of proper names into terms. For example, the terminological meaning of the word "Maldives" as luxury maritime tourism, "Dubai" as shopping and high-end tourism, and "Alps" as a winter tourism brand is the result of a semantic nomination process. The terminological meaning of geographical names expands the concept of a brand in the field of tourism and increases the cultural and semantic load of terms.

The semantic features of tourist terms also reflect the existence of synonymous and antonymic relations in the terminological system. Semantic oppositions such as "tourist"–"traveler", "guide"–"tour leader", "luxury"–"budget", help to more accurately understand the meaning of terms and perceive their intra-system relationships. These relationships play an important role in building a terminological network and allow the use of semantic grouping methods in the learning process.

As a result, the semantic features of tourist terms demonstrate the multidimensional semantic structure of the terminological system in this area, its contextual variability, cultural and functional significance, as well as the dynamic development of the language. Each of these features requires a special methodological approach to teaching terms and is of great importance in the formation of students' professional language skills.

Mastering the terms in the learning process:

Mastering the terms in the learning process is a key stage in the formation of students' professional lexical skills in the field of tourism education. Effective mastering of terms is not limited to studying their lexical and structural features, but also includes their application in real-world practice, communicative situations and professional contexts. In this regard, the learning process is carried out in two main directions: lexical and semantic development and functional and practical use [9].

At the lexico-semantic stage, students analyze the origin of terms, lexical structure, morphological and semantic features, synonymy and antonymic relations. Examples of the use of terms in context, visual and textual materials, as well as their connection with real situations in the tourism industry contribute to the understanding of semantic connections and the assimilation of terms within the framework of the content. At the same time, teaching students verbose combinations of terms, metaphorical and metonymic expressions, as well as contextual meaning develops semantic flexibility.

At the functional and practical stage, the use of terms is adapted to real tourism activities. This includes role-playing games, situational models, preparation of travel packages, modeling of hotel reservations, dialogues with tourists, training in guide activities and the service process. These methods develop students' ability not only to memorize terms, but also to use them situationally and purposefully. The practical approach emphasizes the functional aspects of the terms, enhances students' professional communication and decision-making skills.

The use of modern pedagogical technologies makes the assimilation of terms more effective and visual. These methods clearly demonstrate the structural and semantic features of terms, increase the level of students' perception and make the learning process interactive and interesting.

Thus, the development of terms in the educational process should be based on the integration of didactic and practical aspects, a gradual and systematic approach, as well as the possibility of application in accordance with real professional activities, and should form the professional terminological competence of students in the field of tourism. This approach provides both a deeper understanding of the terms and the development of professional language skills, as well as improves the quality of tourism education.

Conclusion. The analysis shows that the classification of tourist terms from a didactic point of view forms an important scientific and methodological basis for the systematic teaching of terminological knowledge in this field. The creation of a didactic classification based on criteria such as content orientation,

origin-principle, functional-applied orientation and degree of complexity creates conditions for the comprehensive development of both linguistic and professional aspects of terms. These criteria open up wide opportunities for students to apply terms not only at the level of explanation, but also in real-world communication situations, as well as for mastering professional vocabulary in various sub-sectors of the tourism industry [10].

Conclusion. The study shows that the high proportion of international terminology in the field of tourism makes didactic classification even more necessary and ensures the correct use of terms in multilingual communication. Grouping terms by origin, functional structure, and level of complexity increases the gradualness, consistency, and effectiveness of the educational process, and contributes to the formation and strengthening of students' professional vocabulary. Thus, the didactic classification of tourism terms can be assessed as a scientific and methodological approach that remains relevant both pedagogically, linguistically and professionally, creating a methodological basis for tourism education and strengthening the professional competencies of students.

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